

“What are my options”-concept

Referred to as: Watmagweltijdenscrisis.nl

*A collaboration between VeiligheidsRegio
Rotterdam - Rijnmond & Tilburg University*

Design document

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Prototype 'Platform X'

During the COVID19 pandemic, various measures have been introduced to control the spread of the virus. These rules in general reduce the interaction and increase the physical and social distance. However, over time it becomes increasingly harder for people to follow these rules. Tiredness sets in, and socio-economics pressures make people question the efficacy of the rules¹. To shift the narrative it is also important to provide information to citizens, tailored to their information needs. Not only emphasizing the rules, but also the possibilities². This is further explained in this Concept note developed with the Safety Region Rotterdam-Rijnmond.

This document introduces the prototype to demonstrate a *possible* implementation of the concept described in this guidance note. It shows how some of the requirements could be translated into specific functions and features. The functional focus of the prototype is mainly on demonstrating the concept of a 'directory'. Specifically a library where users could find ideas and inspiration relevant to their specific context. From this directory further links can be made to more information (partner organizations) or additional features added to improve the directory itself (user-generated content).

Case study & Further development

The prototype is currently tailored to the Dutch Corona response, and uses content relevant to that context. Scenarios for example are based on the Dutch Corona Roadmap ('[Routekaart](#)'), and events (Christmas 2021, and New Years eve). This prototype is further developed and evaluated for and with the [Safety Region Rotterdam-Rijnmond](#). However, the design and structure of the prototype is such that it could be adapted to any region or context.

The prototype and related concept presented are currently under development and are being further explored. The prototype may be extended with further functionalities and technical improvements. In this document some specific directions for further development. Most importantly however, are the underlying concepts and ideas of offering specific, actionable information to the public.

Relevant links

The concept note:

- <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4320815>

The source code and documentation is available at GitHub:

- <https://github.com/kmeesters/COVID-empowered>
- The code is covered under [GNU GPL V3 license](#).
- Contributors can submit tickets for feedback and submit pull requests to improve the code.
- Other requests and contributions can also be delivered via: k.j.m.g.meesters@tilburguniversity.edu

The prototype itself can be accessed via:

- <http://dev.watmagweltijdenscrisis.nl/> (open on mobile phone for web-app)
- Be aware the bugs may occur and data may be deleted. Do not use this in production environment.

¹ [Do we learn from a crisis?](#) - Kenny Meesters, 2020, Tilburg University

² [Show people what is still possible despite the corona rules](#) - Kenny Meesters, 2020, Tilburg University

Functional requirements

The application consists of three modules, each with an own set of functionalities for specific set of users: a public module (for visitors), a frontend module (for users to control their content), an admin module (for moderation and settings).

Public module

The public module is accessible without any password or login. Through this module the users can access the various ideas, based on certain filters they set, including the events, scenario and focus group. Based on those criteria the module returns a list of matching ideas.

Description	Mockup	Implementation (Laravel)
<p>Home screen: This screen provides a selection of the events or activities to the user (sorted by date, first occurring first).</p> <p>The events are shown first (entry point in the application) as this is the closest to the user-intent (undertake an activity)</p>		
<p>Filter screen: In the next screen the user can add filters, using for example their focus group or the relevant scenario. These filters are stored throughout the session so they only have to set them once.</p>		

Idea list: Based on the set filters the application will filter down specific ideas. The list can also give additional information such as the number of votes received.

Finally it provides the user with a link to a submission form to submit ideas, as they may get inspired from the list and want to share their own ideas.

Idea detail: At the detail page users can find more information and instructions, including links to external websites or video-clips. Users can also report the idea to the moderators, up-vote the idea.

From the specific idea, 'sharing'-links are also available enabling users to share the idea directly to social media.

Submission & Management module

The second module provides options for users ('providers') to submit, update and administer their ideas. While ideas can be submitted via the public site (through a form), this module offers an environment in which authorized users can manage their ideas, update the information, and administer the feedback. Users can form teams in this module so they can collaborate on the ideas. This environment would for example be used by partner organizations of the safety region such as neighbourhood communities, civic organizations or government agencies.

Description	Implementation (Laravel)
<p>Team management: The module provides options to create and manage a team. The team admin can add and remove team-members. This allows multiple people within an organization to work together on various ideas. For example partner organizations can be issued an own team.</p>	<p>The dashboard shows a table with columns: ID, Name, Email, Email verified at, Approved, Verified, Roles. It lists users like 'Kenny Meesters' and 'Admin'. A modal titled 'Toon Leden' displays details for a selected user, including their ID, name, email, and roles.</p>

Idea Management: In the ideas management the team can work together to administrate the ideas they have created (submitted). They can also submit new ideas which -after approval from the administrators- can be made publicly available.

Naam idee	Idee gepubliceerd	Afbeelding idee	URL idee	Gekoppelde activiteiten	Gekoppelde scenario's	Gekoppelde doelgroepen
Zoommetten	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		https://www.rijnmondveilig.nl/	Kerstmis	Ernstig Zeer ernstig Lockdown	Gezin Studentenhuis
Virtuele kerstman	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			Kerstmis	Ernstig Zeer ernstig Lockdown	Gezin Studentenhuis Zelfstandig wonderende ouderen
Kindervuurwerk	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>			Oud & Nieuw	Waakzaam Zorgelijk Ernstig Zeer ernstig	Gezin Studentenhuis
Idee van Kenny	<input type="checkbox"/>		https://www.propus.nl	Caraval	Waakzaam Zorgelijk	Gezin Zelfstandig wonderende ouderen
D'n Otopocht	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		https://www.omroepbrabant.nl/	Caraval	Zorgelijk Ernstig Zeer ernstig	Gezin Studentenhuis

Administration module

The administration module is the 'backend' of the application and accessible by the administrators and moderators assigned by the platform provider. The backend provides options to manage the taxonomy from which the filters are built. Also the ideas can be moderated (modified, (un)published, removed). Also the teams and users can be modified from here.

Description

Idea moderation: admins can moderate incoming ideas, including revising, deleting or publishing them. If needed they can also intervene in the voting casts in case fraud or mis-use is detected.

Implementation (Laravel)

ID	Naam Idee	Idee gepubliceerd	Afbeelding Idee	URL Idee
81	Virtuele kerstman	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
71	Kindervuurwerk	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		https://www.rijnmondveilig.nl/onderwerpen/vuurwerk/?raad-em-2021#--text=Tijdens%20de%20jaarstelling%202020%202020
31	Idee van Kenny	<input type="checkbox"/>		https://www.propus.nl
2	D'n Otopocht	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		https://www.omroepbrabant.nl/
1	Zoommetten	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		https://www.rijnmondveilig.nl/algemeen/veilig-dineren-tijdens-

Taxonomy editor: The admin module also provides options to add/remove categories used to classify the ideas and offer the filter to the end-user.

ID	Scenario Name	Scenario Url	Scenario Published
5	Lockdown		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4	Zeer ernstig		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3	Ernstig		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2	Zorgelijk		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
1	Waakzaam		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

User administration: Admins can also administrate the users on the platform, including the teams, users allocated to those teams and other settings for publishing and user account control (such as roles and permissions).

Statistics: (currently developing) In the statistics, administrators can find various data on the use of the application. For example which ideas are most commonly visited, the click-through rates (indicating if users want to know more), and the drop-out (users leaving without visiting ideas). This information can create a better understanding of the information needs of the users (see 'future development')

Prototype

Implementation

Framework: The prototype has been implemented in Laravel (v8), a popular PHP framework using a model-view-controller architecture. The framework has several built-in features and can be easily extended using libraries. Specifically for the prototype features offered by the framework have been used:

- **Access control:** Allow the creation of users, roles and permissions, enabling a fine grained control who is allowed to perform certain functions. This provides the options for a separate 'editor' role for managing the contents and submissions.
- **Accessible/ RESTful API:** Enabling other applications and programs to access and manipulate the data via an API (secured via an OAuth module). This enables for example the creation of separate applications for users.
- **Modular structure:** The aforementioned groups of functions are developed in separate modules within the framework, allowing distributed development or even be separated in different apps.

User interface: The user interface of the application is using the CoreUI template, based on the commonly used Bootstrap framework. This ensures that the layout and interface is familiar to the user and makes it easier for them to navigate the app.

- **Progressive Web App (PWA):** The public interface is delivered as PWA, allowing the users to install the application on their mobile devices and delivering a 'as native' application.

Hosting: The application is currently hosted on a Heroku development server using a ClearDB MySQL database. Files are stored and hosted on Amazon S3 storage. This first paid tier provides a basic environment secured through an SSL certificate (needed for the PWA delivery). Any server that provides options to host Laravel applications, a MySQL database, upload files and send email would be suitable.

Considerations

Safety & Security: The framework (Laravel) offers various built-in security measures. Furthermore the prototype includes options to define and allocate specific permissions to different user-roles (ACL). It also includes an audit log, tracking every modification of the database. Moving into production a careful revision of the security should be put in place to prevent malicious content being inserted in the system.

Content & Moderation: This also applies to the careful monitoring of the content and settings on the platform by moderators. In the prototype these interactions and possibilities for user-generated content are limited reducing the risk. In a full deployment it is recommended to use an incremental roll-out of the systems, starting with trusted providers for ideas and a small group of users. Once the platform has sufficient content and has been tested this can be further expanded.

Data-model

- Ideas:** The ideas are the main content of the application, and provide specific inspiration and insights for the users to undertake a certain activity during an event. These ideas can be contributed by the community or public. Idea-data can be extended to include for example:
 - Voting & Comments:** Indicate the quality of the idea, for example upvotes by users, or suggestions / comments on the ideas.
 - Partners:** Specific links to organizations, civic organizations, companies, tutorials or other (online) resources that can help the user in implementing the idea.
- Events:** Events are specific activities, such as public holidays or other key activities. Examples include Christmas holidays or Birthdays, but also key activities that are not date-bound such as shopping or sports. The event-data can be expanded with:
 - Categorization:** A more granular classification of the events/activities to support the user in finding the relevant activities.
 - Highlight:** The option to highlight certain events or
- Classifications:** Various classifications or categorizations needed to map the events to certain criteria used by the user to find relevant ideas. This taxonomy in the initial prototype includes:
 - Scenario:** a set of combined rules, guidelines and measures that describe what is possible and not possible. This is for example based on roadmaps or 'tiers' developed by the government. One scenario can be defined as 'current' (default).
 - Focus group** (target audience)
 - Other possible extensions for the taxonomy include: location,
- Administration:** Data related the management of the application such as user management, permissions, and logs.

Entity-Relationship Diagram

A full data-model is available on the GitHub page of the prototype

Future developments

Technical developments

There are various options and possibilities for the further development of this prototype. Two main categories for further development can be initially defined: (1) further improving the relevance of the information presented to the user especially if the list of ideas become more extensive, and (2) adding more interaction and community features providing more interaction in the platform, increasing the quantity and quality of the content.

Improving information relevance: Various technologies can be employed to tailor the information presented to the user to their information needs. These technologies however should come with careful consideration for privacy and data ethics.

- **Further localization & filters** (*under development*): The events and ideas can be further localized, offering more relevant ideas tailored to the local context of the user. Some activities may only be available in a specific region or depend on the capacities/capabilities of the user. For example activities organized in a community center, or ideas that require certain equipment. The taxonomy can be expanded to include more filter options, and can be combined with mobile-specific technologies (localization technology) to help the user filter down specific options.
- **Statistics** (*under development*): As basic implementation of usage statistics could already help to identify which ideas users frequently visit, how engaged they are (for example click-through rates). This would help to identify popular ideas. This information could in turn lead to a better understanding of the information needs of the users. For example which kind of ideas they search for most often, which ideas seem to be of most interest. From these insights additional ideas can be generated or solicited to further support the specific needs or interests of the user.
- **Subscription services** (*under development*): As the platform becomes more dynamic and ideas will be added over time, some ideas relevant to the users will be added later. A basic subscription service (for example through a notification service) can alert users that new ideas are available. Users can for example when a certain filter provides no results, users can indicate they would like to be notified later when ideas are available matching those filters.
- **Linked events and ideas** (*in design*): Some ideas and events may be linked or have a relationship. The application could support the cross-linking between ideas. For example, recommendations based on other users, or supplemental/complementary ideas. This may enable the user to 'browse' and jump between ideas getting more inspiration.
- **Intelligent matching** (*in design*) : The matching between the user-context and the ideas can be further enhanced, especially if the list of ideas becomes large enough. Using user-profiling (either manual for example through a survey, or automatic for example from social media platforms), specific, and more relevant, ideas can be offered to the user. This may also be linked to the aforementioned localization.

Improving information (idea) quality & quantity: Functionalities may be added to the application to add more interaction, allowing users to contribute to the available content. At the same time, tracking the use of applications can also be used to understand which ideas are popular and thus what the users are looking for. However, such functionality requires a strict moderation and content-control policy.

- **Open surveys:** A quick feature to be introduced is to ask users searching for ideas why certain ideas are not relevant, or match their situation. For example if filters return too little results, users can find a suitable suggestion, a button could be shown 'tell us what you are looking for'. This information could be presented to the idea-providers (teams) so they can develop new concepts.
- **Active idea solicitation:** From the insights gained above ('statistic') the provider of the application or their partner can ask for specific ideas in certain categories that are either underserved (users search but limited follow-through) or identify popular ideas that could be expanded on. From the insights gained a more tailored and informed approach to getting new ideas could be implemented including open solicitation, prize incentives etc.
- **Voting & commenting:** An ability may be added for users to vote on certain ideas enabling a sorting based on popularity. This could also help filter out less relevant ideas for the users. At the same time, this voting would help to further improve the understanding of the users and their information needs and thus enable the idea-providers to tailor their ideas better. Likewise commenting could help users and providers to find and improve the quality of the suggestions.
- **Separate modules & integration:** At a more technical level, the application is currently an integration of all modules. However this may be separate in the future to offer more scalability and faster development cycles. At the same time such separation would also make it easier to integrate specific components with other systems. Certain data (like the idea-list) could be integrated in other applications or platforms for example.

In the end the application could eventually become an interactive demand (need for suggestions) and offer (ideas provided) matching platform. Through the platform suggestions and requests for ideas can be exchanged. However this comes with a strong warning, akin to any web2.0 platform and social media technology specifically.

System adoption and roll-out

The system proposed in this document and the overall concept note is but one possible implementation of the concept note. It is mainly meant as an illustrative example used to solicit feedback and initial testing of the concept. Interested parties are welcome to create their own version and implementation of these ideas (provided the required [attribution](#)).

Even more, it can be deployed by different organizations at the same time. Each instance may cater to a specific region or local context. In short, it is not envisioned to have 'one app to rule them all'. Rather the concept can be part of or integrated with other initiatives and does not have to be a stand-alone platform. In fact linking to existing initiatives or structures will make it easier for users to find the app and/or solicit ideas or idea-providers.